

Crack detection around a hole in a cross-ply laminate using an embedded polarimetric fibre optic sensor

H.Wang¹, S.L.Ogin¹, A.M.Thorne¹, G.T.Reed² and M.Ussorio¹

¹*School of Engineering,*

²*School of Electronics, Computing and Mathematics*

University of Surrey

Guildford, Surrey GU2 5XH, UK

Abstract

Polarimetric fibre optical sensors have been used to detect matrix crack development around a circular hole in a cross-ply laminate. The sensors were embedded within the 0° ply, and close to the 0/90 interface, of transparent GFRP coupons. With the aid of in-situ video photography, it has been shown that in all cases when a crack passes the sensor, the sensor detects the crack. Cracks that do not pass the sensor remain undetected. It has also been shown that the use of Fast Fourier Transform and band-pass filtering can be used to detect crack development, suggesting that the polarimetric sensor could be used as an inexpensive damage-monitoring tool for composite structures in real time.

Keywords: **polarimetric fibre optic sensor, cross-ply laminate, crack detection**

1. Introduction

Structurally integrated optical fibre sensors are an important part of smart structures. The primary interest in such sensors is to monitor as many thermomechanical parameters as possible but these sensors are also the subject of intense interest for detecting various types of damage in composite materials [e.g. 1-5].

In this work, a polarimetric fibre optical sensor, fabricated using highly birefringent (Hi-Bi) fibres, has been employed. In contrast to some other types of fibre optic sensors currently under investigation [e.g. 1-4], the polarimetric sensor is an integrating sensor and the gauge length of the sensor can be manufactured to suit the size of the host structure. The lateral strain sensitivity of the sensor is high and it is this property that enables damage such as matrix cracking to be detected.

In the polarimetric sensor, the optical core of the Hi-Bi fibre transmits orthogonally polarised components of light with different velocities. A change of strain state in the host material will affect the strain state in the fibre core, and hence the relative phase of the orthogonally polarised optical signals. The subsequent interference of these signals results in a dynamic change in the output signal which can be used for damage detection.

A schematic diagram of the polarimetric sensor used in the present study is shown in Figure 1. Linearly polarised light is launched into the optical fibre core parallel to one of the orthogonal modes (A). The initial light intensity is I_0 . At the first 45° splice (B), the fibre is rotated 45° so that after the splice both modes are now excited equally. The light intensities in both modes are identical, i.e.

$I_1 = I_2 = \frac{1}{2} I_0$. The fibre is rotated a further 45° at the second splice (C) with the result that the light

in both modes now interferes. The relative phase of these interfering modes, $\Delta\phi$, is determined by the change of strain state in the core (which affects the refractive indices of the two modes) and the length

of the fibre from the first 45° splice to the second 45° splice. The light intensity in mode 1 is $I_1' = I_0 \cos^2\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{2}\right)$ and the light intensity in mode 2 is $I_2' = I_0 \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{2}\right)$. The summation of these light intensities equals the original light intensity, of course, because no energy is lost during the propagation of the polarized light. To avoid measuring the sum of both modes at the detector, bending or looping of the fibre (at D) ensures that one of these modes is removed so that only one set of interference fringes is obtained. The gauge length of the sensor is determined by the distance between the two 45° splices, i.e. the distance between B and C.

Figure 1. A schematic diagram of an embedded polarimetric sensor

In previous work [5], it was shown that such a sensor could detect the development of matrix cracking in a cross-ply laminate. The present study is concerned with detecting the development of matrix cracking damage around a circular hole within a cross-ply composite laminate tested under quasi-static loading.

2. Experimental Arrangement

In this work, polarimetric fibre optical sensors made of Panda fibre (Fujikura Europe Ltd) have been embedded in cross-ply laminates using a wet lay-up/frame winding technique [6] which produces an optical sensor embedded within the 0° ply of a cross-ply laminate and near the 0/90 interface. Coupons with dimensions 20 mm × 220 mm were cut from the laminate and a circular hole with a diameter of 8 mm was drilled at the centre of the coupons. In each case, the cutting of the coupons and positioning of the hole ensures that the sensor is positioned parallel to the length of the coupon and at a distance of 3-6 mm from the hole edge. Aluminium end tags with a length of 20 mm are bonded at both ends of the coupons, as shown in Figure 1. The grips of the fatigue machine have been modified to accommodate the optical fibres emerging from the coupon ends. The 0° plies have a thickness of 1 mm, and the full thickness of the central 90° ply is about 2.5 mm. A 50 mm gauge length extensometer is used to monitor the strain.

A schematic of the experimental test arrangement is shown in Figure 2. Linearly polarised light generated from a He-Ne gas laser source with an operational wavelength of 633 nm is launched into the lead-in fibre; the lead-out fibre is connected to a photo amplifier by a standard connector. The output signal from the amplifier is converted to a voltage and recorded simultaneously throughout the test, together with the load and strain signals, by the controller of an Instron servo-hydraulic 8000 testing machine operating at a sampling frequency of 1 kHz. A digital video camera (Panasonic NV-GX7B) was used to record each test with a time resolution of 0.04 s. Time on the controller and video

was synchronised by gently tapping the extensometer in the view of the digital camera at the beginning of each test. The visible tap recorded on the digital camera was matched to the resultant spike seen in the recorded strain signal, enabling individual cracks recorded by the digital camera to be related to the signals recorded by the Instron controller. The video camera and the Instron test machine are started manually and hence there is always a small, but accurately known time difference between the time recorded by the camcorder and the time recorded by the Instron test machine. Quasi-static testing of coupons was carried out with the Instron servo-hydraulic testing machine (8000) operating under load control mode.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the experimental arrangement

3. Experimental results.

3.1. Detection of initial cracks around a circular hole

When a coupon with an embedded sensor is loaded quasi-statically, optical fringes are recorded as the applied strain increases [7]. In coupons with a central hole, the first matrix cracks develop from the edge of the hole due to the local strain concentration.

Figure 3 shows a plot of strain and optical output against time, together with frames from the digital camcorder that show the development of the first three cracks. The strain signal shows a generally linear increase with time as the load increases, whilst the output signal from the sensor is sinusoidal as a result of the optical fringes. The strain output over this time interval during the test (from about 11 seconds to 18 seconds) shows three small step changes. These increases in strain were related to the development of cracks with the aid of the frames from the digital video recording. The step change at about 13 seconds corresponds to crack 1, which developed on the left side of the hole. The step change at about 15.9 seconds, corresponds to the development of crack 2 which occurs on the right-hand-side of the hole, and the third step change corresponds to crack 3 which, like crack 1, develops on the left side of the hole. The embedded optical sensor, which runs parallel to the length of the coupon to the left of the hole, is not visible at this magnification, but the position of the sensor was delineated on the surface of the coupon with a marker pen. It can clearly be seen from the optical output that it is only the crack that develops on the sensor side of the hole, i.e., crack 2, which causes a step change in the optical response (the step-change is a characteristic feature of crack detection using the polarimetric sensor [5]). Cracks 1 and 3, which develop on the side of the hole away from the sensor do not affect the optical output of the sensor.

Figure 3. Detection of initial cracks around a circular hole in a cross-ply laminate. (a) Strain and optical output signals of Crack 1, 2 and 3; (b) Cracks development recorded with a digital camcorder. Only crack 2, which passes the sensor, produces a change in the optical output.

3.2. Detection of transverse cracks occur in other positions

At higher loads, transverse ply cracks develop at places other than the stress concentration provided by the hole. Figure 4 shows the optical, strain and visual identification of three such cracks that developed in a different specimen. Again, the position of the sensor has been delineated on the coupon surface with a marker pen.

Figure 4 shows the strain, optical output and relevant video frames for the development of the cracks labelled 4, 5 and 6. The crack labelled number 4 propagates across the complete width of the coupon instantaneously and a step change occurs in the optical output that corresponds both with the strain change and with the video recording of the crack development. Crack 5, on the other hand, propagates only part-way across the coupon width, but the crack passes the sensor and hence a step-change in the optical output is recorded which is simultaneous with the strain change. By contrast, crack 7 initiated from the left-hand edge of the coupon and stopped before it reached the position of the sensor. In this case, although a strain change was recorded, there was no step-change in the optical output.

Figure 4. Detection of cracks in other positions. (a). Strain and optical output signals of Crack 4, 5 and 6. (b). Cracks development of Crack 4, 5 and 6 recorded with a digital camcorder.

3.3 Fourier analysis of the optical output.

The previous results have shown that damage development can be detected in composite materials using the polarimetric sensor. Frequency analysis of the optical signals demonstrates that crack detection can also be achieved in real time. As a demonstration of this potential, a frequency analysis of the optical output, comparing time periods when cracks occurred or did not occur, was carried out. A Fast Fourier Transform (executed within the ORIGIN® program), and a band pass filter, were used to determine the exact time and frequency of signals associated with crack development. As Figure shows, the characteristic frequency for these specimens was about 93 Hz, and a band pass frequency of 70-130 Hz was used to block out the effect of lower and higher frequencies. Applying this procedure to the data, the band pass filtered signal showed a peak when each crack developed, and hence showed a history of crack development. Figure 6, for example, shows the result when cracks 4 and 5 developed. Peaks are clearly visible at times that correspond to step changes in the optical and strain outputs.

Figure 5. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis of the optical output signal. (a) FFT analysis of the optical output signal when no cracks occurred; (b) FFT analysis of the optical output signal when a crack occurred

Figure 6. Band pass filtered optical signal and optical output as a function of time

A practical implementation of this procedure would require that a real-time FFT is performed on the optical output from a polarimetric sensor embedded in a composite structure. Such a system would enable the damage in a composite structure under load to be detected by the sensor.

4. Discussion

It is well known that when a transverse ply crack grows across a laminate as a result of mechanical loading, two effects produce an immediate increase in length of the coupon. Firstly, the compressive thermal strain within the 0^0 plies is relaxed around the crack producing a lengthening of the specimen. Secondly, in addition to this local relaxation of thermal strain, the compliance of the specimen increases as a result of crack formation, producing an additional increase in specimen length [8, 9]. If the cracks occur within the extensometer gauge length, these changes in length will be recorded by the extensometer as a step change in strain, as shown in Figure 4. The servo-hydraulic testing machine is operating under load control, so that when the strain suddenly increases, leading to a drop in load, the servo-hydraulic machine corrects the load to the demand signal. This fluctuation of load on the coupon will generate a global strain change on the coupon [5].

These strain variations have two effects on the sensor. First, when a crack occurs, there is a strain

magnification in the 0^0 ply, adjacent to the crack [10]. In these experiments, the polarimetric sensor is positioned close to the 0/90 interface and hence will experience a sudden large local change in strain state as a result of the crack passing the sensor. Secondly, the global strain change in the coupon induced by the crack will produce a longitudinal strain change in the sensor. Any strain change will contribute to the phase change of the sensor's optical output. However, only those cracks that developed on the same side of the hole as the position of the sensor produced a change in the optical output. Furthermore, cracks that do not pass the sensor (such as cracks 1, 3 in Figure 3 and crack 6 in Figure 4) do not produce a change in the optical output. This means that the step optical signal changes are induced by the complex interaction between the strain field around the matrix crack in the immediate vicinity of the crack tip and the embedded sensor.

The polarimetric sensor is an integrating sensor. As a result, the magnitude of the change in the optical output as a consequence of the growth of a matrix crack past the sensor depends on the integrated effect of the local strain changes on the path difference for the "fast" and "slow" axes of the sensor. However, there is an added complication in that the Hi-Bi Panda fibre used to manufacture the sensor has optical axes that define the "fast" and "slow" directions for light in the core; the orientation of these axes with respect to the axes of the composite is thus an additional variable. The prediction of the magnitude of the change in the optical output as a result of the passage of a crack is the subject of current work.

Finally, it should of course be pointed out that detection of matrix cracks developing from both edges of a hole would require two polarimetric sensors, one either side of the hole, or for the sensor to be looped around the hole.

5. Conclusion

A polarimetric fibre optical sensor can be used to detect matrix crack development around a stress concentration in a composite laminate. Characteristic step changes in the optical output occur when a crack grows past a sensor which are due to the interaction between the strain field changes induced by the passage of the crack and the optical fibre. Crack detection using this sensor can form the basis of a real-time damage monitoring technique.

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